

UGC Care Listed

त्रैमासिक साहित्यिक पत्रिका

ISSN-2321-1504 Nagfani

RNI No. UTTHIN/2010/34408

वर्ष-12, अंक-42, जुलाई - सितम्बर 2022

भाग-2

75
आज़ादी का
अमृत महोत्सव

नागाफनी

मूल्य
₹ 150/-

अस्मिता, चेतना और स्वाभिमान जगाने वाला साहित्य

भाग - 02

नागफनी

A Peer Reviewed Refereed Journal
(अस्मिता चेतना और स्वाभिमान जगाने वाला शोध-साहित्य)
UGC Care Listed त्रैमासिक साहित्यिक शोध पत्रिका
ISSN-2321-1504NaagfaniRNI No.UTTHIN/2010/34408

संपादक
सपना सोनकर

सह संपादक
रूपनारायण सोनकर

Co Editor(English)
Prof.Rajesh karankal
Dr.Santosh Kumar Sonkar

कार्यकारी संपादक
डॉ.एन.पी.प्रजापति
प्रोफेसर बलिराम धापसे

वर्ष-12 अंक 42, जुलाई-सितम्बर-2022 भाग -2

सलाहकार मण्डल (Peer Review Comittee)

प्रोफेसर विष्णु सरवदे, हैदराबाद (तेलंगाना)
प्रोफेसर आर. जयचंद्रन तिरुअनंतपुरम (केरल)
प्रोफेसर दिनेश कुशवाह, रीवा (मध्य प्रदेश)
डॉ.एन. एस. परमार, बड़ौदा (गुजरात)
प्रो. दिलीप कुमार मेहरा, बी.बी.नगर (गुजरात)
डॉ.उमाकांत हजारीका, शिवसागर(असम)
डॉ. आर. कनागसेल्वम, इरोड (तमिलनाडु)

प्रोफेसर संजय एल. मादार, धारवाड़ (कर्नाटक)
प्रोफेसर गोविन्द बुरसे, औरंगाबाद (महाराष्ट्र)
डॉ.दादा साहेब सालुनके, महाराष्ट्र (औरंगाबाद)
प्रोफेसर अलका गडकरी, औरंगाबाद (महाराष्ट्र)
डॉ. साहिरा बानो बी. बोरगल, हैदराबाद (तेलंगाना)
प्रोफेसर मोहनलाल 'आर्य' मुरादाबाद (उत्तर प्रदेश)
डॉ.जी.व्ही .रत्नाकर हैदराबाद(तेलंगाना)

प्रकाशन/मुद्रण

प्रकाशक रूपनारायण सोनकर की अनुमति से डॉ.एन.पी.प्रजापति एवं प्रोफेसर बलिराम धापसे द्वारा नमन प्रकाशन-423/A अंसारो रोड दरियागंज, नई दिल्ली 11002 में प्रकाशन एवं मुद्रण कार्य।

मुख्य पृष्ठ- उत्कर्ष प्रजापति, सिंगरौली - मध्यप्रदेश

संपादकीय/व्यवस्थापकीय कार्यालय

दून व्यू कॉटेज स्पिंग रोड, मंसूरी -248179, उत्तराखण्ड, दूरभाष : 0135-6457809 मो.0941077718

शाखा कार्यालय

पी.डब्ल्यू. डी. आर. -62 ए ब्लॉक कॉलोनी बैदहन, जिला-सिंगरौली म. प्र. पिन-486886 मो. 09752998467
सहयोग राशि -150/-रुपये, वार्षिक सदस्यता शुल्क (संस्था के लिए)-1500/-रुपये, पंच वार्षिक सदस्यता शुल्क (व्यक्ति के लिए)-3000/-रुपये, पंच वार्षिक संस्था और पुस्तकालयों के लिए -3500/-रुपये, विदेशों में \$50 आजीवन व्यक्ति-6000/-रुपये, संस्था-10,000/-रुपये

सदस्यता शुल्क एवं सहयोग राशि-इंडिया पोस्ट पेमेंट बैंक-A/C -8367100138282 IFSC Code-IPOS0000001
Branch-sidhi, NIRPAT PRASAD PRAJAPATI

नोट:-पत्रिका की किसी भी सामग्री का उपयोग करने से पहले संपादक की अनुमति आवश्यक है। संपादक-संचालक पूर्णतया अवैतनिक एवं अध्यक्षीय हैं। 'नागफनी' में प्रकाशित शोध-पत्र एवं लेख, लेखकों के विचार उनके स्वयं के हैं। जिनमें संपादक की सहमति अनिवार्य नहीं है। 'नागफनी' से संबंधित सभी विवादास्पद मामले केवल देहरादून न्यायालय के अधीन होंगे। अंक में प्रकाशित सामग्री के पुनर्प्रकाशन के लिए लिखित अनुमति अनिवार्य है। सारे भुगतान मनी ऑर्डर, बैंक/चेक/बैंक ट्रांसफर/ई-पेमेंट आदि से किए जा सकते हैं। देहरादून से बाहर के चेक में बैंक कमीशन 50/- अतिरिक्त जोड़ें दें।

लेख भेजने के लिए -Mail-ID- nagfani81@gmail.com
पत्रिका के बारे में विस्तार से जानने के लिए देखें Website:-http:naagfani.com

Feminist Discourse

1. The Better Man: A Feministic View-Dr. Ashish Gupta 101-102
2. Longevity Paradox: Challenges for the tea garden female workers with special reference to Borsillah Tea Estate In Sivasagar district of Assam-Pallabi Hazarika & Galo Miwu 104-107
3. Double trauma of Kashmiri Women in Nayeema Mahjoor's Lost in Terror-Supriya Bodo & Dr. Indu Swami 108-111
4. Need For Recognition of The Unpaid Domestic Contribution of Women To Quantify Share in Matrimonial Property-Neha Balyan & Dr. Rekha Verma 111-115
5. Historical Aspects of Women's Property Rights in India-Sapna Chopra & Dr. Parag Agarwal 116-119
6. Women and Crime: Intentions behind female criminality-Mercy Hazarika 119-125
7. Women's Political Participation in India -S.K. Abdul Amanullah 126-129

Dalit Discourse

1. There Are a Lot of Dalit Children but Little Childhood: A Study of Childhood in Selected Dalit Narratives-Priyanka Kumari & Dr. Suresh Kurapati 130-133
2. Socio-Economic Status of Schedule Caste in Bihar with special reference to Gaya District-Alok Kumar Singh 134-137

Tribal Discourse

1. A Comparison of Socio-Economic Profile of Tharu with other Tribes in Uttar Pradesh Using Census Data-Bhanu Pratap Pandey & Dr. Anand Sugandhe 138-142

Others

1. Key Informant Relationship with Ethnographic Fieldwork on Folk Art and Craft Clusters in Assam-Dr. Drabita Dutta 143-146
2. Intra District Disparities in School Infrastructure-A Case study at Jorhat District of Assam, India-Mridul Kumar Borah & Sewali Das 147-150
3. The life of the Bhikkhunis in the sangha : An analytical study of Therīgāthā -Monika Raj 150-133
4. Impact of The Pandemic on Higher Education and The Effectiveness of online Education: Special Reference To Rural India-Mrs. SHILPI 153-157
5. Higher Education through the Medium of Indian Languages Opportunities and Challenges: Dalit and Tribal Perspectives-Dr. Suresh Kurapati 157-160
6. Startup India: Challenges and Opportunities-Dr. Vandana Pandey 161-165
7. Changing Pattern of Food Processing Industry in India After Globalisation-Ms. Anchal yadav & Dr. Dushyant Kumar 166-169
8. Analysis of The Controversial Provisions of The Ordinance in Recent Years-Suman & Dr. M. Imran 169-172
9. Performance of Commerce Graduates in Job Market-Nagendra N. & Dr. N. Nagaraja 173-178
10. Seasonal Variation of leaf dust load of Various Plant Species of the main Campus of Kamla Nehru Institute of Physical and Social Sciences, Sultanpur, Uttar Pradesh-Harshita Singh 179-181
11. Value education and spirituality in education-Its relevance in the 21st century modern Education-Jolly Anju 182-184
12. Is Health Communication a New Soft Power of India?-Vivek Kumar 185-188
13. Food Security In India-Mukesh Kumar Meena 188-191
14. Role of Technology in Cyber Crimes: An Assessment-Amita & Dr. Harishankar Rai 192-195
15. Impact of New Economic Policy on Food Processing Industry: A Critical Assessment-Ms. Anchal yadav & Dr. Dushyant Kumar 196-199
16. Some Somatometric Profile Among The Kom Tribe of Manipur-Dr. L. Romeo Singh & Ksh. Sunita Devi 200-206
17. Crop Insurance and Government Programmes Scheme: Does Farmers get Benefit: A Case From Tumkuru -SRIKANTHNAIK H & GIRISHA T & JAYANTH H 207-210
18. A Comparative Study of Job Stress and Burnout Among Male & Female Teachers in Higher Studies-Rohini Mahur & Dr. William 211-214
19. Cyber Crime and Remedial Measures in India Judicing A Comparative Approach Dr. Pravin Kumar Chauhan 214-217
20. Impact of Perception on Performance Appraisal and Job Satisfaction on Employee Performance With Reference to Pharmaceutical Companies in Bangalore-DIVYA K. & DR. K. NAGENDRABABU 218-221
21. Prospects, Problems and Challenges of Indian Ports -SRIKANTHNAIK H & MANASA K N 222-225
22. A Study on the Influence of Job Insecurity on Employee Job Performance: Mediating Role of Organisational Trust-Dr. S. N. VENKATESH & SRIKANTHNAIK H 225-229
23. A study of the social contribution of Raghu Rai's photo journalism-Amit Mishra 223-233
24. Job Stress among Secondary School Teachers of Papum Pare District in Arunachal Pradesh-Monika Sharma & Dr. Ravi Ranjan Kumar & Shriprakash Pal 233-236

The Better Man: A Feministic View

Dr. Ashish Gupta

Professor & Head

Department of English

Government Girls College Betul, India

Anita Nair is one of the eminent women novelists in contemporary India; she has earned honors for her originality, propensity and for her societal dedication. She presents women characters in her novels with full of enormous courage. As an Indian woman and the experiences of women around her she perfectly understood the societal-cultural problems of women. The celebrated author was born at Kundakottakurissi, near Shornur in Kerala. Her works of fiction have been translated into 21 languages. She studied in Chennai before moving back to Kerala, where she obtained a BA in English Literature. She worked as the creative director of an advertising agency in Bangalore. It was at this time in 1977 that she wrote her first book, a collection of short stories titled *Satyr of the Subway*. In fact, the book earned her appreciation and she also won her a fellowship from the Virginia Center for Creative Arts. She has made a debut in children's literature also. Nair has also written *The Puffin Book of Myths and Legends* (2004), a children's book on myths and legends. Nair has also edited *Where the Rain is Born* (2003). Nair's writings about Kerala and her poetry has been included in *The Poetry India Collection* and *British Council Poetry Workshop Anthology*. Her poems appeared in many prestigious poetry anthologies like *The Dance of the Peacock: An Anthology of English Poetry from India*, featuring 151 Indian English poets, edited by Vivekanand Jha and published by Hidden Brook Press, Canada. It is interesting to note that *The Better Man* is a novel by Anita Nair. It is set in the northern part of Kerala, India, a region known as Malabar under the British Raj. *The Better Man* is set in contemporary India in a little fictitious village called Kaikurussi in the northern part of Kerala. This region was once known as Malabar during the British regime. After Independence, Malabar as a geographical region ceased to exist. Though Malabar has no geographical boundaries, no presence on a map of India, it still exists as a state of mind: laid-back, slow, to live and let live. So much so, the northern Malabaris treat the enterprising and hard-working southerners with a disdain bordering on contempt. A person from Malabar is so entrenched in the past that thinking of the morrow is almost impossible. And yet, there is a discontent that is almost palpable. Perhaps this is the reason why the region that was once Malabar saw the growth of

Naxalites [extremists who combined Marxism with violence against all organized systems]; still has the highest recorded number of lunatics and suicides in India and has fundamentalist political groups thriving side by side with communist strongholds.

Notably, Kaikurussi the village is in a little hollow surrounded by several hills. It has nothing there that would make any one come looking for it. It is neither the birthplace of a Mahatma nor a movement. No miracles have ever happened there. In fact, nothing of significance ever happens there to anyone. In fact, there is not even a road running through Kaikurussi or a river flowing alongside it. All Kaikurussi has to define its topography are fields, wells, a mountain and distant hills. An elderly bachelor and a retired government employee, Mukundan is forced by circumstances to return to Kaikurussi, the village he was born in. A village that he fled when he was eighteen. And now back in his ancestral house, he finds himself unable to cope. He is haunted by a sense of failure. For having abandoned his mother. For not measuring up to his still alive and domineering father Achuthan Nair's expectations. For having gone through life without really living it. And then there is the village itself. Mukundan realizes that he has no role to play in the village. In fact, he discovers that what should have been his rightful place had been usurped by an upstart Power House Ramakrishnan. In the first few weeks of his exile, he meets up with a wayward genius. Bhasi or One-screw-loose -Bhasi as he is known is a house painter and a practitioner of a mongrel system of medicine, he has evolved by combining several kinds of healing processes - herbal cures, principles of Homeopathy.... Bhasi is deeply disturbed by Mukundan's anguish and decides to mend the cracks in Mukundan's much battered psyche. He cajoles, manipulates and shapes Mukundan's transformation. But the superficiality of the change is revealed soon. Power House Ramakrishnan on a cruel whim decides to build a community hall in the village. And chooses Bhasi's piece of land as the site to build on. When Bhasi refuses to sell his land, Power House Ramakrishnan threatens to break his business and run him out of the village. As the richest and most powerful man of the village Power House Ramakrishnan was capable of doing just that and

Bhasi knows this as well. So, he turns to Mukundan to intervene on his behalf. Mukundan sets out to save Bhasi's home but is completely swayed by Power House Ramakrishnan. The latter knowing how recognition-hungry Mukundan is and how easily he would succumb to flattery uses that as his weapon to sweep over Mukundan's objections and has him actually agreeing to become a part of the community hall committee. Mukundan betrays Bhasi his friend and alienates Anjana, the woman he is in love with. [Anjana is still married to another man and would therefore be considered an unsuitable love by the community hall committee.] Mukundan however does not perceive it as betrayal and stubbornly clings to the belief that what he has done is right. But it takes the death of Achuthan Nair, his father to make him realize how empty his life was and would continue to be without either Bhasi or Anjana. He is stricken by both remorse and guilt. And the realization that he was no better than his father whom he had despised all his life. With this comes the real transformation. Mukundan decides to make amends. And how he goes about it is an indicator to how much Mukundan has changed. From a fastidious and colorless man lacking in courage to take even the slightest of risks, Mounding becomes a man capable of finding love and happiness. A man who discovers the varied vibrant hues of life. A man who emerges from the shadow of his father's personality to become a better man.

Kit Reed, writing in *The New York Times*, says "A genial, meandering tale filled with false alarms and diversions, *The Better Man* is slowed by loops in the story, by abandoned threads of plot. Charming as it is, the novel gathers momentum only at the end, when Bhasi and Mukundan find themselves at odds just in time for the drama of conflict and resolution." Another review in *The Hindu* said "Anita Nair's first book, *The Better Man*, was a finely structured novel set in a small Kerala village. Mukundan, her hero, returns to the village, hoping to exorcise bitter memories. Anita Nair not only has a wonderful knowledge of life in the village, but shows an almost Dostoevskian feeling for the undercurrents of consciousness, as Mukundan seeks and finds redemption."

The Literary Review column of *The Hindu* said "The *Better Man* had all the right ingredients according to the critics. Today, with her second book *Ladies Coupe*, one would imagine ANITA NAIR would have achieved the same results. Critics have opined otherwise..." As already stated Anita Nair is an Indian best-selling author of Indian poetry with her famous novels, "*The Better Man*" and "*Ladies Coupé*". Born in Kerala and raised in Chennai. Anita always had an affinity towards writing and the courage to pursue it under all

the situations. In every novel, Anita Nair thought about the woman's search for freedom and realization. In Anita Nair's fictions, her characters have come out of their struggles and quest their identity. Her Novels explore the freedom of the man to fulfill herself basically as a human being, independent of her various traditional roles as a daughter, wife, mother and so on. This article deals with self-discovery as seen in the works of women writers. Here it must be remembered first that as a Indian Writing in English has placed an independent status in the realm of Indian literature. Fictionary writing in Indian English. Women writers occupy a major role in the contemporary writing in Indian English. Women writers come away from traditional portraits of enduring -sacrificing women toward conflicted female characters searching for identity and defined their victory. Anita Nair is one of the finest writers in writing in English.

It is pertinent to note that Valsala in "*The Man*" is the wife of Prabhakaran, an aged school teacher. Valsala is not satisfied with him. So, she falls in love with Sridharan. She doesn't bother about the consequences. She realizes her inner mind and becomes the mistress of him. This incident shows the femininity of Valsala in the form of morality. As a matter of fact she is aware of the fact that every woman needs an ergizer of love, freedom, equality and sex. She justifies herself as, "I am just forty years old. I want to be pushed into old age before its time. I want to live. I want passion. I want to know ecstasy. I told herself, night after night" (Nair 130). Valsala emerges as a "New Woman". A woman who breaks the traditional Indian society. So, she is usually satisfied with her affair with her neighbor Sridharan and does not feel guilty of it. Valsala achieves an identity in life but against the traditional manner. Valsala resorts to freedom not only politically but sexually too. When she resolves her inner conflicts, she is able to conquer self-identity. The second character Anjana, in the novel "*The Man*" was grown up in a beautiful atmosphere. She was married to Ravindran, at the age of twenty. She has lost all her independence in the name of marriage. Her married life is not good. Whenever Anjana is ready for conversation, Ravindran feels irritated and leaves the place. She longs for love and freedom. Her marriage ends in failure. So, she develops to hate things including herself. Notably, one day Anjana goes to her parent's home in order to look after her mother. This gap becomes an escape from her traditional life. Ravindran's business failed and he decided

Ravindran doesn't care about her and grows unsteady and dismal. By seeing this gap, Anjana's father raised a voice against him. "When I hope that you would love her. Cherish and protect for the rest of her life. If all you intend to do is hurt and made her unhappy, then there is no need for a relationship. My daughter can manage very well without a husband like you". (Nair, BM: 232). As Anjana's father finds a suitable teacher job, she comes out of her married life. She comes to realize that life can always be made possible. Now, Anjana becomes a mature woman. The writer tries to examine that patriarchal set up which is responsible for the man's condition in the Indian society. The novel also shows the growth of the character from weakness to maturity. Anjana wants healthy life and degree of control over her life, as an educated woman. "She gave away her beautiful sarees and took to wearing starched cottons in which as insipid and dull as her life. She locked up all her jewellery in a safe deposit box in the bank and threw all her fripperies away into the waste basket". (Nair, BM: 234). Ultimately, Anjana comes over the traditional Indian consciousness and creates the words for her own. Anjana's emergence from her unsuccessful marriage, with the determination to live as a free individual, is an assertion of her personal freedom. She meets Mukundan and falls in love with him. In Mukundan's company, she realizes that she has to free herself from her unhappy married life. When Anjana confesses her love to Mukundan, he said, "Anjana", Mukundan said, "you must listen to me. It knows you think I am a good man a gentle man. Someone you can depend on completely. I don't know if I am that man, you make me to be. My mother begged me to rescue her and take her away. But I didn't. It was afraid of my father, and so I gave her excuses. If I had done as she asked me, perhaps she would be still alive. That is the kind of man I am. A weak and undependable creature. Do you want to be part of such a man's life?" "All of us have our weakness, but we seldom have the courage to accept them. Or even develop it as you have done now. To me, that makes you braver than anyone else. I love you. My love tells me that you are right for me?" (Nair, BM: 244,245) Remarkably, Anjana seems to be deeply concerned with women's freedom as Anjana wants to stand on her own wishes and liberty. After a long struggle, Anjana turns out to be a woman who can make choices, take decisions and makes up her mind to start a new life with Mukundan. Anjana's positive attitude towards life, work financial

independence, and self-identity helps her to go ahead in her life with hope and optimism. She has also created her gender identity and found a new life with Mukundan. Interestingly, the novel depicts the real women in the form of Anjana who faces all the matters of patriarchy society and then after a lot of suffering in her marriage then she found love when she met Mukundan. Again, she got disappointed when Mukundan denied to accept her before society but this time she become so positive and find her own way to live her life. As such Anita Nair has examined the inner identity of her all-female characters in a psychological way. They could never think that there can be different world outside the four walls of their house. Nair was completely cut off from such dynamic world. The woman living in such a traditional society become so habitual to their surrounding that the marriage is their destiny and their husbands are their master. And their duty is to obey him and serve him and his family. Nair being a woman penetrates deep into the inner mind of the depressed women by their feminine sensibility and psychological insight and bring to light, which are the outcome of Indian women's psychological and emotional imbalances in a male dominated society. To conclude, it may be surmised that self-understanding is an essential part of Indian philosophical and theological systems present here. Self-discovery here is more realization of one's own interests in the narrow sense. It is the significance of place in a fiction that Nair has attempted in her 'thickly populated' first novel, *The Better Man*. Here it must be remembered that the phrase 'thickly populated' specifically aims at sharp characterization and has invented myriad characters like Achutan Nair, 'One-screw Bhasi', Anjana, Power-house Rama Krishna, Meenakshi the Naxalite etc. For Nair it is also the tension between characters that allows the movement of the narrative to progress at a brisk pace. Characterization constitutes the real essence of all her novels. Anita Nair has a real position to write and put them in action. This persuaded and kindled to take up the writings of Anita Nair to examine, revive and study her works and is therefore anticipated to be a ceaseless incident of enrichment and reward.

REFERENCES

1. Dhanyasree M "The Better Man: Review on Anita Nair's Novel". One India.
2. *Marriage and the Working Woman in India*. New Delhi Vikas, 1970.
3. Nair, Anita. p. The Better Man- A Novel by Anita Nair". Anita Nair web site.
4. Nair, Anita: *The Better Man*. New Delhi: Penguin Books India, 1999.
5. Reed, Kit (August 13, 2000). p. Faith Healer. *The New York Times*.
6. Sinha, Sunita. *Post-Colonial Women Writers New Perspectives*. New Delhi: Atlantic Publishers and Distributors (P) Ltd: 2008.